

Climate & Water: Main insights of user research

Methodology for Researching User Experience Interaction with the Climate & Water (C & W) Platform

1.1 In the discovery phase of the project, we conducted quantitative research, specifically a survey with closed questions, to determine: what information is prioritized for calculations; what additional data would be useful; to assess the accuracy of managers' theoretical knowledge regarding climate indicators; to evaluate which types of graphs and maps are most convenient and understandable; to find out how users interpret the data; and to gather other useful insights that will help make the product more user-friendly.

The survey included 60 respondents (full report available via the link), was conducted through Google Forms, and contained 51 questions regarding previous experiences with web resources, as well as perceptions and interpretations of scientific information.

Respondents were presented with various types of graphs and maps, and they were asked to evaluate how clear and sufficient the information on them was for describing a particular process. Examples of graphs include:

1. This graph shows historical and expected changes in river water withdrawals in a closed basin *

Please rate whether you feel the graph format should suit your needs if similar information was provided for the river basin in your region.

Fig. 1. Historical and hypothetical river water withdrawals data under socioeconomic development scenarios. The best each optimized model is approved first 2016. Data using the best of combinations, and the green and light brown (rest reported data developed using global socioeconomic models (as optimized) COMS.

- Graph contains all necessary information for informed decision making.
- Necessary information is present, but additional explanation is needed for efficient information
- Necessary information is partially absent, and key details are missing
- Needed information is completely absent from the graph
- This graphic format is inconvenient or requires improvement
- Unclear how to interpret data for practical recommendations or action
- Other: _____

Рис. 2. Відносна зміна середньорічної витрати води (1991-2020) за сценарієм високих викидів парникових газів (RCP8.5) для ансамблю кліматичних моделей EURO-CORDEX-11.

Рис. 3. Відносна зміна річної витрати води за 5-ма різними кліматичними моделями за умов двох різних соціально-економічних сценаріїв розвитку суспільства (SSP2-4.5) та (SSP5-8.5). Зміни розглядаємо відносно базового періоду 1985-2014.

Рис. 4. Процентні зміни середньорічної витрати води за глобальною ідологічною моделлю WaterGAP2 для двох сценаріїв викидів парникових газів (rcp26 - низькі викиди, rcp85 - високі викиди). Примітка: показує 25-75-й перцентилі можливі сценарії за різними кліматичними моделями, горизонтальна лінія - медіана, вертикальні лінії - мінімальні та максимальні значення.

Examples of maps:

3. This map shows projected runoff changes within basin

Please rate whether the presentation format shown would suit your needs if similar information was provided for the river basin in your region.

Fig. 7. Percentage change in mean runoff during 2021-2440 period relative to 1991-2020 for the representative concentration pathway RCP8.5 as ensemble climate models developed using

- Map contains all necessary information for informed decision making.
- Necessary information is present, but additional explanation is needed for efficient information use.
- Necessary information is partially absent, and key details are missing.
- Needed information is completely absent from the map.
- Unclear how to interpret data for practical recommendations or action.
- This graphic format is inconvenient or needs improvement.
- Other:

Questions regarding the understanding of data and the approach to its assessment. These questions helped us prioritize information on the Climate & Water platform and add functionality that better addresses the core challenges of the target audience, as well as communicate data in terms that are most comprehensible to the user.

- What information about changes in water resources under future climate scenarios would be most useful for your operational and planning activities?
- Please specify 1-2 most devastating impacts of climate change on Ukraine's water resources in your opinion.
- What are the main challenges you face in managing the river basin in your region under climate change?
- Do you have sufficient information for planning and implementing effective measures to mitigate challenges in your region's river basin?
- From your experience, what difficulties have you encountered when using research or reports that provide information about future climate changes for water resource management?
- What general difficulties have you faced regarding the use of climate change forecasts in water management?
- How are you currently integrating climate data into water resource management solutions? What tools or methodologies are being used?
- How does information about climate forecasts influence your decision-making processes?

Conclusions and insights from the discovery phase of the research.

The survey showed that while water resource managers operate on scientific data, they tend to prefer the simplest ways of visualizing data that are accessible and understandable. For Climate & Water, we need to present data in a way that best meets the needs of the user (manager) of a specific management, and only then show the overall picture.

The challenges of studying the impact of climate change:

45%
Insufficient detail on how the impacts of climate change translate into practical problems.

37%
Difficulties in interpreting general climate change assessments into specific local changes.

53%
Climate forecasts are too uncertain to be useful for long-term planning.

52%
Forecasts are too generalized and not applicable to local or specific contexts.

About understanding graphs and data

Understandable data

48.3% - mostly understandable

50% - completely understandable

Unclear data

23.3% - mostly unclear

16.7% - mostly unclear

Quantitative assessment of responses regarding the clarity of graphs or maps

Feedback and insights

User feedback and insights can be divided into main categories:

1. Quality and clarity of graphs

- The graphs currently appear "cluttered" and difficult to perceive; simpler and clearer visualizations are desired.
- Clear explanations are needed for each graph, as without them, the data is hard to interpret.
- Some graphs are too small or unclear, especially those about droughts, making them difficult to read.
- Some users do not use graphs due to their complexity.
- Some institutions provide more user-friendly graphs, saving time.

User information needs

- Short-term and medium-term data on water expenditures and levels in major rivers, reservoirs, and ponds are required.
- Specific data for water bodies: pools, river sections, reservoirs, ponds are requested.
- Information on different types of water expenditures is needed: evaporation, floods, runoff, the relationship between water levels and expenditures.
- Groundwater levels and temperatures should ideally be presented over 30 years in an understandable format.
- Separate data on evaporation is needed for fish farms.

Observations and monitoring

- Current information and observations on water expenditures over the last 5-6 years are of interest.
- Inquiries about water levels and their exceedances: expected number of objects and impact on the situation.
- It is important to monitor deviations from the water norm over a period of at least 5-6 years.
- Information on water levels and possible flooding scenarios is needed for decision-making.

External factors and risks

- Users want to see warnings and threat assessments: storms, landslides, snowy winters, flooding.
- Data should include information on temperatures, anomalies, and specifics for individual seasons and years.
- It is preferable to focus on local data and models rather than national averages.

Practical remarks on data formatting and presentation

- Clear summaries of water expenditures and simplified tables or infographics are needed.
- Information should be better structured, highlighting indicators for different purposes (agriculture, fish farming, etc.).
- Some respondents request a step-by-step guide on how to use the data and plan water expenditures.

1.2 In the post-launch / Growth phase of the project, we conducted qualitative research, specifically post-release interviews and analysis of user interactions with the product.

Parameter:
Provide data for model 2.

Department:
Buvr River Ros.

Observations:

- easily found model 2
- but requested better highlighting of models, as they did not know it could be turned off.

Possible actions:

36. Highlight models more, add hovers (

37. More prominently highlight the selected one or add a label, such as "You have selected this."

Department:
Buvr Pryazovya.

Observations:

- easily found the model.

From these observations, those that serve as a starting point for improvements were identified. They were divided into groups according to areas of responsibility: Scientists first, Only the developer, Design first, We need to discuss. For each issue, a description and the results of the team's brainstorming were added — further actions to improve interaction with the product.